

EUREKA

European Knowledge Repository for Best Agricultural Practices

D4.4 - FarmBook platform with code/installation
documentation & user guide

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History of Changes

Date	Changes
27/08/2022	Added new content regarding the Single Page Application (4.3) and front-end development on page 9.
	Added Annex 1, our front-end coding guides and ruleset, pages 17-23
	Added Annex 2 which is the development readme file with its listed dependencies, page 24
	Added Annex 3 regarding development automation using NPM, page 25

TASK 4.4

Summary

This task involved the actual front-end development of the platform. This task uses the product requirements document from T4.1, as well as the UI/UX design from T4.2 to build the platform and connects to the Data Repository that will be built in parallel in T4.3. The platform will be developed using an agile development methodology, SCRUM - which is characterized by the division of tasks into short phases of work and frequent reassessment and adaptation of plans. In SCRUM, development was executed during two-week sprints, starting with a sprint planning to determine which work will be done (using the backlog as input) and ends with a sprint retrospective in which the achieved results are presented to relevant stakeholders, such as end users, the EC and consortium partners, to gather early feedback. As part of T4.4, extensive documentation will be created allowing for easy installation and modification of the EU FarmBook by administrators of the platform.

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EUREKA

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
EIP-Agri	Agricultural European Innovation Partnership
FG	Focus Group
KR	knowledge reservoir
IA	Innovation Action
MAA	multi-actor approach
MAP	multi-actor project
OG	Operational Group
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
TN	Thematic Network
WP	Work Package
API	Application Programming Interface
REST API	Representational State Transfer API
Solr	(Pronounced "solar") is an open-source enterprise-search platform, written in Java

1. Introduction

This deliverable is written with the front-end developer in mind as they are the only ones who need access to the software application code environment. We consider a front-end developer as anybody who can read and write software application code. To provide the developers with the most up-to-date information we will often make references to existing knowledge databases which are continuously update. We've done this by including a user guide in this deliverable.

Additionally, we also explain how previous deliverables from the EUREKA and EURAKNOS projects have been integrated throughout the front-end development and finish with a critical analysis of the current setup and how we plan to use these learnings in the follow-up project.

2. Integration of gained knowledge: EU FarmBook development from EURAKNOS to EUREKA

Four deliverables from the EUREKA and EURAKNOS projects have been important to the front-end development.

Knowledge from D2.3 (EUREKA - Report on end-user archetypes, end-user journeys and validation workshops), D4.1 (EUREKA - Product Requirements Document) and Task 4.5 (User Testing and Optimization of FarmBook) was used by the UX-researcher involved in writing these deliverables during weekly development meetings and close interaction with the development team.

Knowledge from D4.3 (EUREKA - FarmBook data repository and search engine with code/installation documentation and a user guide) and D3.2 (EURAKNOS – Report on HIKR design) was used in weekly development meetings by the authors of these deliverables.

3. Platform (front-end) development

For a thorough description, documentation, and explanation of the software architecture we refer to D4.3, where all technical building blocks were tackled.

The repository and search engine are the foundational components we built upon throughout the development of the EU FarmBook 'EUREKA' or 'pilot' version. The data structure and Apache Solr instance (search engine) were chosen based on open-ended API's and a flexible and functional front-end application that help to maximise interoperability.

We made use of the [Scrum methodology](#) for organising the development process of the platform. This methodology aims to give the full development team the power and responsibility to break down the work in smaller pieces. This has a few advantages:

1. By creating smaller subtasks. It is easier to test & validate smaller portions of work more often.
2. We have a rhythm of 'sprints' in the team. This makes for optimal amount of communication and collaboration.

3. There is more flexibility to adapt to new information, gained learnings or unforeseen circumstances without wasting a lot of time in redoing work.

This is the opposite of working in a ‘waterfall’ method, where we would have done the full technical analysis first on deliverables of earlier deliverables. In this method, we would not have been ready for new insights and learnings during the development of the platform. This is crucial for projects where ground-breaking work is being performed and new learnings (on the content-aspect and on the technical-aspect) happen on a daily basis.

4. User guide and documentation of the front-end development

This guide makes the EU FarmBook portal easily accessible for further development and will assist possible administrators / front-end developers to:

- Setup the platform on their local machine
- Perform code quality checks
- Build new features and extend them in the existing technological landscape
- Build these features to the production portal / EU FarmBook

To do so we have listed the following 5 relevant topics, ranging from a user guide to data interactions (the API) towards the final deployment of code on the different environments.

Remark: We have provided a more thorough explanation of our technological landscape and choices in the deliverables D4.3; our focus in the following topics lies on the relevant information to start working with the system.

4.1. The user guide – a functional description

The understanding of a platform lies in more than just its technical documentation. Therefore we’ve created a functional user guide that lists all available functionalities on the front-end side of the platform, providing a clear overview on all functionalities that are currently available, and where they can be found in the EU FarmBook.

This guide can initiate team members in the available first step in a more thorough understanding of our work and can be found on the following link: https://drupal.eufarmbook.eu/sites/default/files/2022-06/20220328_manual_eufarmbook.pdf

4.2. The API

We’ve opted for a well-documented and open-source REST API. The following documentation will allow developers to easily understand and read the choices we’ve made throughout the development process.

4.2.1. Drupal 9

Easy content authoring, reliable performance, and excellent security are standard features of Drupal. But what sets it apart is its flexibility. Its tools help you build the versatile, structured content that dynamic

web experiences need. You can extend it with any one, or many, of thousands of add-ons, or integrate Drupal with external services and other applications in your infrastructure. No other content management software is this powerful and scalable.

The Drupal project is open-source software. Anyone can download, use, work on, and share it with others. More than a thousand organisations collaborate to build Drupal and its extensions.¹

Our open-source Drupal 9 middle layer enriches the data from the repository with automatic translations, static interface copy, image enrichment and the mapping of User Generated Content (*likes, comments, threads, experts*). It performs a gateway function to the world wide web using the well-documented, -used and -known Contenta API. This industry standard makes it possible for web-developers to easily read and understand our codebase.

4.2.2. Contenta API

Contenta is an API-First Drupal distribution that provides an out of the box content model, which is considered to be an industry standard in the Drupal landscape. More information on the Contenta CMS, ranging from goals to demos and development guidelines, can be found on: <https://contentacms.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>.

As a more technical reference, and thus directed towards developers, a Public Github can be frequented on: https://github.com/contentacms/contenta_jsonapi allowing for even more in-depth clarifications such as readme files, open issues, forks, security updates and more.

4.2.3. Swagger.io

To make our API automatically documented, we've integrated Swagger as a well-known and widespread solution. Swaggers allows for maintainable (automatically generated) documentation. More information on swagger can be found on: <https://swagger.io/solutions/api-documentation/>.

Our own Swagger instance for the EU FarmBook can be found on the following link: <https://drupal.eufarmbook.eu/admin/config/services/openapi/swagger/jsonapi>.

The link above describes all API calls that are being consummated by the EU FarmBook platform, allowing for a 360° view on all available REST API calls, delivered in JSON format.

4.3. Single Page Application (Vue JS / Nuxt JS / NodeJS (NPM))

Front-end development is the visual layer of the web application, where all interaction happens. It's where the platform lives, where technical data and design meet and your web application becomes functional. The interface was built as a so-called SPA (Single Page Application). This type of application allows web browsers on the client to load the application and use it from there without ever needing to (re)render the interface on the server.

The user experience greatly benefits from this type of behavior.

More specifically we built upon the latest (stable) version of the NuxtJS (<https://nuxtjs.org/>) framework, which extends the very popular and open source Vue JS (<https://vuejs.org/>) framework.

¹ Source: The official Drupal website, <https://www.drupal.org>

In the end, as an end result, this code is compiled into just 3 things: HTML, CSS and JavaScript. These are the things that every browser can interpret and display on the end user's screen.

Vue JS

Vue (pronounced /vju:/, like **view**) is a JavaScript framework for building user interfaces. It builds on top of standard HTML, CSS and JavaScript, and provides a declarative and component-based programming model that helps you efficiently develop user interfaces, be they simple or complex.

Relevant documentation of the framework can be found on: <https://vuejs.org/guide/introduction.html> and is described in a more elaborate fashion in D4.3, as was mentioned earlier.

Nuxt JS – installation guide

Nuxt JS is an open source Vue JS framework that enables a more efficient and powerful development experience. More information on the installation of the framework can be found on the following link: <https://nuxtjs.org/docs/get-started/installation/>.

Readme file

Additionally, we've provided our own installation guide in the following README file, which can be made available via username and password for all new administrators / front-end developers of the platform. It elaborates further on the setup and installation of EU FarmBook platform from a front-end perspective.

The aforementioned readme file can be viewed in the Annex 2 that was added to this document.

Build and tooling automation (Javascript stack)

In order to automatize our building and tooling approach we have used the well-known NPM package manager which is an open source, well documented and standardized platform. More information on Node JS (Javascript) language and the package manager can be found below:

About Node JS

Node.js Is An Open-Source And Cross-Platform JavaScript Runtime Environment. It Is A Popular Tool For Almost Any Kind Of Project!

Node.js Runs The V8 JavaScript Engine, The Core Of Google Chrome, Outside Of The Browser. This Allows Node.js To Be Very Performant.

A Node.js App Runs In A Single Process, Without Creating A New Thread For Every Request. Node.js Provides A Set Of Asynchronous I/O Primitives In Its Standard Library That Prevent JavaScript Code From Blocking And Generally, Libraries In Node.js Are Written Using Non-Blocking Paradigms, Making Blocking Behavior The Exception Rather Than The Norm.

More information on NodeJS can be found on the following link: <https://nodejs.dev/en/learn/>

About NPM

Npm² is the world's largest software registry. Open source developers from every continent use npm to share and borrow packages, and many organizations use npm to manage private development as well.

npm consists of three distinct components:

- the website
- the Command Line Interface (CLI)
- the registry

Use the [website](#) to discover packages, set up profiles, and manage other aspects of your npm experience. For example, you can set up [organizations](#) to manage access to public or private packages.

The [CLI](#) runs from a terminal, and is how most developers interact with npm.

The [registry](#) is a large public database of JavaScript software and the meta-information surrounding it.

More information on how NPS can be used can be found in Annex 3: Build Flows

² <https://docs.npmjs.com/about-npm>

4.4. Code commenting

By default, we've provided readable code and, where necessary, code commenting is used to provide additional explanation of business logic. Keeping comments close to the code makes it readable for other developers.

Below you can find an example of how our comments are built up:

```
main.scss 544 Bytes
```

```
1 // =====
2 // Main
3 // =====
4 // Specify character encoding, must be the first item!
5 @charset "utf-8";
6
7 /**
8  * Load in all main styling, order is very important here. Config should always
9  * be on top, followed by core and then base. Then utils - layouts - components
10 * - scopes.
11 */
12 @use "./config";
13 @use "./core";
14 @use "./base";
15 @use "./utils";
16 @use "./layouts";
17 @use "@components";
18 @use "./scopes";
```



```

1 // =====
2 // Definition
3 // =====
4
5 /**
6  * Private colors: HSL based colors. The hue and lightness are reflected in
7  * naming. DO NOT USE THESE COLORS OUTSIDE THIS FILE.
8  */
9
10 $_gray-97: hsl(220, 43%, 97%); // #F5F7FB
11 $_gray-94: hsl(0, 0%, 94%); // #F0F0F0
12 $_gray-85: hsl(220, 10%, 85%); // #D6D8DD
13 $_gray-54: hsl(216, 6%, 54%); // #828992
14 $_gray-15: hsl(208, 21%, 15%); // #1E272F
15
16 $_black-0: hsl(0, 0%, 0%); // #000000
17
18 $_white-100: hsl(0, 0%, 100%); // #FFFFFF
19
20 // Farmbook
21 $_teal-46: hsl(193, 27%, 46%); // #568896
22
23 // Ui
24 $_green-39: hsl(160, 84%, 39%); // #10B981
25
26 $_orange-95: hsl(38, 100%, 95%); // #FFF6E6
27 $_orange-94: hsl(16, 94%, 94%); // #FEE8E0
28 $_orange-58: hsl(15, 95%, 58%); // #FA6330
29 $_orange-30: hsl(14, 61%, 30%); // #7B341E
30
31 $_blue-48: hsl(216, 98%, 48%); // #0365F4
32
33 // Forestry
34 $_teal-95: hsl(200, 11%, 95%); // #F0F2F3
35 $_teal-80: hsl(186, 10%, 80%); // #C8D1D2
36 $_teal-23: hsl(182, 34%, 23%); // #264C4D
37 $_teal-18: hsl(182, 35%, 18%); // #1E3E3F
38
39 // Crop farming
40 $_red-95: hsl(24, 100%, 97%); // #FFF5EF
41 $_red-84: hsl(25, 41%, 84%); // #E7D4C6
42 $_red-35: hsl(12, 65%, 35%); // #953820
43 $_red-29: hsl(13, 64%, 28%); // #752E1A
44
45 // livestock
46 $_green-96: hsl(94, 33%, 96%); // #F4F8F1
47 $_green-89: hsl(77, 31%, 89%); // #E6EBD9
48 $_green-23: hsl(68, 100%, 23%); // #647400
49 $_green-19: hsl(71, 100%, 19%); // #4E5F00
50
51 // Climate
52 $_yellow-97: hsl(45, 50%, 97%); // #FBF9F3
53 $_yellow-91: hsl(42, 55%, 91%); // #F5EEDD

```


4.5. Deployment and environments

4.5.1. Drupal deployment flow

We've built in an automatic deployment flow, which enables our developers to follow this standardised approach:

- New code is first validated on the test - and later the acceptance - environments.
- When validated and tested, the code is pushed to the master branch on bitbucket (git versioning).
- Our automatic deploy flow ensures a build of this newly validated code to the production version of the platform.

More information on this PAAS solution can be found on: <https://docs.platform.sh/integrations/source/bitbucket.html>

4.5.2. Front-end deployment flow

Deployments of the Nuxt (Vue JS) application are done as a single-page application. This means that there are no specific hosting requirements besides hosting files. Building the application is provided by the Nuxt setup. The documentation we've provided earlier in section 4.2 also contains the steps to build the application to a hostable set of files.

We automate our build-and-deploy process by making use of Bitbucket Pipelines. This makes use of a Docker-powered environment where the application is built in a temporary and safe environment.

The different steps of this process are written in the <bitbucket-pipelines.yml> file in the codebase of the platform. This is an industry-standard.

The following links contain relevant information:

- <https://support.atlassian.com/bitbucket-cloud/docs/get-started-with-bitbucket-pipelines/>
- <https://www.docker.com/resources/what-container/>

5. Conclusions

A clear takeaway we'd like to share towards the extension of the current project and platform (i.e., the project 'EU FarmBook' granted under Horizon Europe, call HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01-24³: 'Supporting knowledge exchange between all AKIS actors in the Member States by means of an EU-wide interactive knowledge reservoir', is that we want to make a clear distinction between the front-end application and the business logic (middle layer). This means that in our future platform we would follow a different approach:

- All business logic (including the UGC, translations, ...) will be handled in the business layer, which means that there will be one API (data) layer, without any additional middleware.
- All customer facing / interface logic is written in the front-end Single Page Application, which is very similar to the current setup. This enables to keep the same user experience, focusing on speed, agility, and motion.
- The issue of multilingual functionality is of increased importance for the EUREKA FarmBook platform. To this end, important steps have already been taken within the EUREKA project aiming to enable access to the platform's interface and interaction from the side of the users in a range of EU languages (i.e., English, French, German, Dutch, Spanish, Italian, Polish, Danish, Estonian, Greek, Hungarian, Lithuanian, Slovenian, and Romanian). In the follow-up project, access to the platform's interface will be enabled in all the languages formally spoken in the EU by using state-of-the-art automated translation facilities. Moreover, the option of translating the actual content of Knowledge Objects (wherever applicable) will also be explored by taking stock of Natural Language Processing tools and models. Finally, the advantages of storing Knowledge Objects in the FarmBook by having their metadata available in all EU languages (as opposed to translating them on the fly to provide Knowledge Object-related background information to the users) will be explored.
- The stack of the technologies used for the development of the EUREKA FarmBook's platform will be revisited and decisions will be made about the technology components to keep and technology components that should be replaced by other solutions to meet any future needs regardless the scale effectively and efficiently at which access to information and knowledge should need to be accessed.
- Hosting infrastructure can be more centralised. This will not only improve performance for the end-user, but also will also benefit the troubleshooting of potential problems and reduce the SPOF's (Single Points of Failure) as well as the overall costs of operating and maintaining the platform.

³ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-cl6-2021-governance-01-24>

6. Annex I: EUREKA FarmBook (Front-end) coding guidelines and explanations

This Annex section provides code examples and guidelines on how the codebase was formatted and structured throughout the application. These guidelines should be used and followed for additional development and extensions. This keeps the codebase accessible, interchangeable, and interoperable for future development.

6.1. Linters

Linters are rulesets that check and validate our code for inconsistencies. These can run during development or before committing. We highly recommend fixing any type of warnings these linters generate.

These linters help out and respect the guidelines. The linters are configured to safely tell us when we are not following these "reasonable" rules.

6.1.1. Stylelint

For styling in CSS or SCSS, stylelint is used. We have a package that contains a ruleset to follow: [@littlemissrobot/stylelint-config](#)

scss/css:

```
module.exports = {
  "extends": [
    "@littlemissrobot/stylelint-config"
  ]
}
```

6.1.2. Eslint

For templating in JavaScript, eslint is used. We have a package that contains a ruleset to follow: [@littlemissrobot/eslint-config](#)

es6:

```
module.exports = {
  "extends": [
    "@littlemissrobot/eslint-config",
    "@littlemissrobot/eslint-config/linters/es6"
  ]
}
```


Vue:

```
module.exports = {  
  "extends": [  
    "@littlemissrobot/eslint-config",  
    "@littlemissrobot/eslint-config/linters/es6",  
    "@littlemissrobot/eslint-config/linters/vue"  
  ]  
}
```

Nuxt:

```
module.exports = {  
  "extends": [  
    "@nuxtjs",  
    "plugin:nuxt/recommended",  
    "@littlemissrobot/eslint-config",  
    "@littlemissrobot/eslint-config/linters/es6",  
    "@littlemissrobot/eslint-config/linters/vue"  
  ]  
}
```

6.1.3. Comments

These rules should be respected and applied when commenting code.

Comments must not exceed the limit of 80 characters per line, to respect readability:

```
// This is a line of comments that will not exceed 80 characters  
  
/**  
 * This is a multiline comment block that will not exceed 80 characters.  
 * This is a multiline comment block that will not exceed 80 characters.  
 * This is a multiline comment block that will not exceed 80 characters.  
 */
```

6.2. HTML

This is a small guide explaining on how we like write HTML to keep it readable and manageable.

We barely ever just write plain HTML. For this we make use of templating languages like Nunjucks. This allows us to write variables, functions, conditions, define reusable blocks, include or import certain HTML blocks.

6.2.1. Nunjucks

Nunjucks is a templating language, backed by Mozilla, that is JavaScript based. We mainly use it within simple setups when simple sites like static sites need to be quickly created. We also have a Storybook setup that utilizes the functionality of this language. For example, defining a component:

```

```html
{# ===== #}
{# Definition #}
{# ===== #}

{% macro default(data) %}

 {# Props #}

 {% set classes = data.classes if data.classes else "" %}
 {% set size = data.size if data.size else "" %}
 {% set isDisabled = "is-disabled" if data.isDisabled else "" %}
 {% set text = data.text if data.text else "" %}

 {# Component #}

 <button
 class="c-button {{ classes }} {{ size }} {{ isDisabled }}"
 {% if isDisabled %} disabled {% endif %}
 >

 {{ text }}

 </button>

{% endmacro %}
```

```


6.2.2. Ruleset

We do not have a big list of rules when defining HTML. Instead, we simply try to keep our indenting and tags as clear as possible and to add comments when necessary. These are just a few examples; a more in-depth list can be found in the next guidelines section.

6.2.3. Tags on the same line

We try to avoid writing tags on the same line because it does not help with readability. It also makes it difficult to see where the tag ends. For example:

```
<!-- This is hard to read and difficult to know when it ends. -->
```

```
<p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Aenean euismod, odio et imperdiet dapibus, ipsum ligula facilisis nisl, eu viverra erat dolor at neque. Nam non urna quis ipsum sollicitudin rutrum.</p>
```

```
<!-- This is easier to replace and to know when the tag start and ends. -->
```

```
<p>
```

```
    Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Aenean euismod, odio et imperdiet dapibus, ipsum ligula facilisis nisl, eu viverra erat dolor at neque. Nam non urna quis ipsum sollicitudin rutrum.
```

```
</p>
```

6.2.4. Spacing between children

When writing HTML, we try to place return characters (spacing) between child definitions in a parent tag. This is done purely for readability of the code. Whenever two or more children follow each other within the same container, we separate them from each other. If there is just one, then we keep everything appended onto the parent. It also makes it easier to select and replace content. For example:

```
<!-- We try to add returns to separate the children: -->
```

```
<section class="l-section">
```

```
  <header class="l-section__header">
```

```
    <hgroup class="l-section__header-group">
```

```
      <h1>
```

```
        Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.
```

```
      </h1>
```

```
      <h2>
```

```
        Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Aenean euismod, odio et imperdiet dapibus, ipsum ligula facilisis nisl, eu viverra erat dolor at neque.
```

```
      </h2>
```

```
    </hgroup>
```

```
  </header>
```

```
<footer class="l-section__footer">
```

```
  <a class="c-link" href="#">
```


Link

</footer>

</section>

6.3. CSS

This guide is focused on explaining on how we like to write CSS in SASS. It explains which principles we use and what we focus on when writing CSS and how our setups are defined.

CSS is hard to manage and can get dirty very fast if not properly maintained. To keep this language clear and readable we try to follow certain principles like BEM to structure the code. It is therefore the responsibility of the developer to keep it clean and readable.

6.3.1. Sources

- [CSS guidelines](#)
- [SASS guidelines](#)
- [BEM](#)
- [BEMIT](#)
- [Specificity](#)

6.3.2. System

We have defined our own [system published on NPM](#) for handling design tokens like colors, typography, utils, grid, breakpoints, etc. The topics in this guide are all included in this system. (Read on about this system in our guide)[<https://bitbucket.org/leapforward/little-miss-robot-devops-guide/src/master/sass-system/>].

6.3.3. BEM

[BEM](#), short for Block Element Modifier, is a naming convention to describe and define classes in HTML and CSS. It improves the readability and helps unfamiliar developers understand what a component does.

6.3.4. Block

The root or the top-level abstraction of a component. For example:

```
<button class="button">
```

```
</button>
```

```
<header class="header">
```

```
</header>
```



```
<footer class="footer">
</footer>
```

6.3.5. Element

Elements can be considered as the children of the block. They are placed inside the Block and are denoted by `<_>`, followed by the name of the child. These children cannot be used outside of the Block element. For example:

```
<button class="button">
  <span class="button__text"></span>
</button>
```

```
<header class="header">
  <div class="header__title"></div>
</header>
```

```
<footer class="footer">
  <p class="footer__copyright"></p>
</footer>
```

6.3.6. Modifiers

Modifiers are classes that modify or adjust the Block and its children. This is shown by appending `--` to the name of the block or child. For example:

```
<button class="button button--secondary">
  <span class="button__text"></span>
</button>
```

```
<header class="header">
  <div class="header__title header__title--dark"></div>
</header>
```

```
<footer class="footer footer--invertd">
  <p class="footer__copyright footer__copyright--small"></p>
</footer>
```


6.3.7. Example

To better explain this, below is an example of a fixed article component using the BEM principle. The main component is called `article` and has different children and modifiers. It also makes use of the `link` component within its `article__footer` Element/Child, which has its own styling.

```
<article class="article article--inverted">
  <div class="article__container">
    <header class="article__header">
      <h1 class="article__title article__title--dark">
        Article title
      </h1>

      <h3 class="article__subtitle">
        Article subtitle
      </h3>
    </header>

    <p class="article__text">
      Article description, this can be lorem ipsum :D
    </p>

    <img class="article__image article__image--fluid" src="" alt="" title="" />

    <p class="article__text article__text--secondary"></p>
    <footer class="article__footer">
      <a class="link link--fill-space" href="">
        Lees meer
      </a>
    </footer>
  </div>
</article>
```


7. Annex 2: EUREKA FarmBook (Developer) readme file

This Annex section provides development installation guides for the front-end web application, it is also provided as a readme file in our bitbucket pipelines as was mentioned earlier.

Install – readme

This readme file gives brief instructions to developers on how to setup and run the front-end web application.

1. Clone from `git clone [repo]`
2. `npm install` to install all dependencies
3. `npm run start` to start developing

NPM – dependencies⁴

When You Install An Npm Package Using `Npm Install <Package-Name>`, You Are Installing It As A Dependency.

The Package Is Automatically Listed In The Package.Json File, Under The `Dependencies` List (As Of Npm 5. Previously, You Had To Manually Specify `--Save`).

When You Add The `-D` Flag, Or `--Save-Dev`, You Are Installing It As A Development Dependency, Which Adds It To The `DevDependencies` List.

Development Dependencies Are Intended As Development-Only Packages, That Are Unneeded In Production. For Example Testing Packages, Webpack Or Babel.

When You Go In Production, If You Type `Npm Install` And The Folder Contains A `Package.Json` File, They Are Installed, As Npm Assumes This Is A Development Deploy.

You Need To Set The `--Production` Flag (`Npm Install --Production`) To Avoid Installing Those Development Dependencies.

Annex 3: Build flows

⁴ <https://nodejs.dev/en/learn/npm-dependencies-and-devdependencies/>

8. Annex 3: EUREKA FarmBook (Developer) automation

8.1. NPM (Node Package Manager) – guide⁵

8.1.1. Use npm to . . .

- Adapt packages of code for your apps, or incorporate packages as they are.
- Download standalone tools you can use right away.
- Run packages without downloading using [npm](#).
- Share code with any npm user, anywhere.
- Restrict code to specific developers.
- Create organizations to coordinate package maintenance, coding, and developers.
- Form virtual teams by using organizations.
- Manage multiple versions of code and code dependencies.
- Update applications easily when underlying code is updated.
- Discover multiple ways to solve the same puzzle.
- Find other developers who are working on similar problems and projects.

8.1.2. Getting started

To get started with npm, you can [create an account](#), which will be available at http://www.npmjs.com/~*yourusername*.

After you set up an npm account, the next step is to use the command line interface (CLI) to [install npm](#). We look forward to seeing what you create!

8.1.3. Sharing packages and collaborating with others

If you choose to share your packages publicly, there is no cost. To use and share private packages, you need to upgrade your account. To share with others, create organizations, called [npm organizations](#), and invite others to work with you, privately (for a fee) or publicly (for free).

You can also use a private npm package registry like [GitHub Packages](#) or the open source [Verdaccio](#) project. This lets you develop packages internally that are not shared publicly.

8.1.4. Learn more

To learn more about npm as a product, upcoming new features, and interesting uses of npm be sure to follow [@npmjs](#) on Twitter.

For mentoring, tutorials, and learning, visit [node school](#). Consider attending or hosting a nodeschool event (usually free!) at a site near you, or use the self-help tools you can find on the site.

⁵ <https://docs.npmjs.com/about-npm>

8.1.5. CLI reference documentation

While relevant CLI commands are covered throughout this user documentation, the CLI includes command line help, its own [documentation section, and instant help \(man pages\)](#).

More information on all relevant packages and modules can be found on: <https://docs.npmjs.com/packages-and-modules>

